

science and policy
for a healthy future

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WP5 - Translation of results into policy

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1 Introduction

“The HBM4EU project has entered a very exciting year” says prof. Dr. Greet Schoeters (VITO, HBM4EU co-coordinator and science-to-policy pillar leader). “After four years of hard work, we can finally start to share results.”

On 28 and 29 of April 2021, an online workshop was organised on the first HBM4EU research results on PFAS, one of the HBM4EU priority substance groups. The goal of the workshop was to discuss the results with a selected group of scientists, risk assessors and risk managers, to define main messages for policy making and to explore how the results can support ongoing policy processes, both at the EU- and the national level.

Because part of the results were only preliminary and not yet publicly available at the time of the workshop, it was only possible to organise a closed and confidential workshop, with researchers from the consortium, representatives of the national HBM studies that are part of HBM4EU, and representatives from various DGs of the European Commission and EU agencies. In total, 56 participants took part in the workshop, with a very stable number of participants during both half days. Annex I contains the participants' list.

The workshop was a collaborative effort of partners from different work packages and HBM4EU pillars, and supported by the HBM4EU Management Board. Presentations were given by HBM4EU partners and by key actors in ongoing risk management processes. See Annexes for the full program and participant list.

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2 Day 1 - Messages from HBM4EU on PFAS

On the first half day of the workshop the participants were welcomed by prof. Dr. Ilse Loots (UAntwerp, workshop host and WP5.5 lead) and Dr. Marike Kolossa-Gehring (UBA, HBM4EU coordinator).

“From the start of HBM4EU, linking science and policy has always been a major goal. The exciting challenge of these two days will be to see how our answers to policy questions will be taken up by those who will push forward chemicals policy in Europe, and which questions they will in return have for our consortium.” Marike Kolossa-Gehring (UBA, HBM4EU coordinator)

2.1 Overview of HBM4EU activities on PFAS

In a first presentation, **Dr. Maria Uhl** (EAA, PFAS Chemical Group Leader in HBM4EU) gave an overview of all activities performed in HBM4EU related to PFAS. This includes exposure monitoring, research into health effects, as well as a lot of work behind the scenes to develop a harmonised and quality controlled HBM network in Europe. As a teaser, Maria also presented results from a recent Austrian mother-child HBM study, in which 61 individual PFAS were analysed in maternal blood, placental tissue and cord blood, as well as analysis of extractable organic fluorine, a measurement for total PFAS.

- Link to [Research Brief: HBM4EU work on Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances \(PFAS\)](#)
- Results from the [Austrian mother-child study](#)

2.2 HBM data on PFAS exposure in Europe

In a second presentation, **Eva Govarts** (VITO, WP10 data management) presented an overview of available HBM data on PFAS in Europe, as well as a (confidential) preview on PFAS results from the HBM4EU aligned studies, i.e. HBM studies from various countries in Europe that have been aligned to generate EU-wide HBM data.

Data from ‘existing’ HBM studies (*previous to HBM4EU*) were collected and harmonised, and were recently made available in an [interactive dashboard](#) on the HBM4EU website (since March 30, 2021). In the dashboard, summary statistics on 19 PFAS compounds from 17 different datasets can be consulted and stratified for basic characteristics.

However, comparing the different datasets should always be done with caution, because of differences in study designs, sampling periods, age groups and analytical methods. Results from these studies were also sent to EFSA in 2019, in the context of a public consultation for the EFSA opinion on 4 PFAS compounds (2020).

Results and conclusions from the ‘aligned’ HBM studies are not yet publicly available, because the data were only recently pooled into one database and more detailed statistical analysis is still needed. Results will become available early 2022. In first instance, HBM based indicators will be calculated and communicated (expected early 2022).

Subsequently, more detailed analysis results will become available in several scientific publications in the course of 2022. The aggregated data itself are available to the HBM4EU project partners via the internal webpages and will be available to authorised users via IPCHEM (expected early 2022) and will be made publicly available at the end of the project (June 2022) via the HBM4EU dashboard and IPCHEM.

- Link to [The European Human Biomonitoring Dashboard](#) on the HBM4EU website
- Results from aligned studies will become available in the course of 2022

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Discussion on main messages for communication of ‘aligned studies’ results

After the presentation with first results from the aligned studies, participants to the workshop were asked to reflect on the main messages for communication of the results. Given the confidential nature of these results, we do not disclose the proposed main messages in this report. Results will become available in the course of 2021. However, the feedback from the workshop participants can be summarised as follows:

- When comparing data with **health-based guidance values**, the general message should be that these values are set to be protective for the entire population (including all population groups and all potential adverse effects). However, for some audiences it is also important to specify on which scientific basis these values were derived (What is the critical effect? Which type of studies were used? ...).
- For policy makers (i.e. politicians) and the general public, it is important to include information on **actions that can be taken**, both to prevent emissions to the environment as well as to prevent personal exposure. This information about sources and exposure routes can be obtained from modelling work. And reference can be made to (existing) background documents summarising the current knowledge about the substance group.
- When communicating about **socio-demographic differences** in internal exposure, or other exposure determinants, the main focus should be on characteristics that citizens or policymakers can act upon. For example, a difference between men and women is only a basis for action if it can be explained by differences in behaviour, lifestyle or exposure conditions.
- It is also desirable to communicate about **scientific challenges and remaining uncertainties**. And why it is important to invest resources in the reduction of remaining uncertainties.

2.3 Health impact of PFAS exposure

After a short break, several other research results were presented.

Stella Fragki (RIVM) presented a review work on the association between PFOS/PFOA exposure and increased blood cholesterol and altered lipid profiles. This association has been repeatedly observed in humans, but a causal relation has been debated. Within HBM4EU an attempt was made to unravel the mechanism of action relevant for humans. Although no clear mechanistic explanation was found, important pathways were identified to be further investigated.

“Future studies with human-relevant test systems and realistic exposure levels would help to obtain more insight into the mechanistic pathways pertinent for humans. HBM data will be important for these studies, also for other PFAS” says **Stella Fragki** (RIVM)

- Results of this study have been [published](#) and similar mechanistic studies are underway for other health endpoints (immune system and reduced birth weight).

Prof. Dr. **Thorhallur Ingi Halldorsson** (University of Iceland) presented results of epidemiological studies performed within HBM4EU on the association between PFOS/PFOA exposure and

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infections and other immune outcomes. With regard to the immune function, the current focus of European risk assessments is mainly on reduced antibody response following vaccination in human studies, clearly strengthen this observation.

However, studies on the link with infections have been less consistent, partly because it is more difficult to study. A recent study clearly demonstrates the association of enhanced PFAS concentrations of pregnant women with increased risk of hospitalisation of their offspring due to infections. Epidemiological studies within HBM4EU on infections complement existing findings on antibody response suggesting that higher PFAS exposures may indeed lead to increased propensity for infections.

“For some risk assessors, use of human studies is still considered uncertain or even controversial. Addressing main uncertainties may lead to broader acceptance. In addition, more focused and novel approaches are needed to address other PFAS, ideally using less time and effort.” says **Thorhallur Ingi Halldorsson** (UI)

- Results of a study on maternal exposure to PFAS and hospital admissions of children have been [published](#) and other studies are underway (on use of antibiotics, asthma and allergies and immune cell counts).

In a final presentation, **Wieneke Bil** (RIVM) presented results from an exploratory study of different approaches for PFAS mixture risk assessment and how to make them suitable for estimating risk on the basis of HBM data. Three approaches have been compared and resulted in similar conclusions. However, some of the approaches are better suited for future refinements and extension to more PFAS, based on HBM data.

“All three approaches, using human biomonitoring data, lead to the same conclusion and support the need for risk management measures. The results raise awareness to treat PFAS as mixtures, also in drinking water, soil, etc. Further refinement and extension of the assessments will be needed, by using HBM data from the aligned studies” says **Wieneke Bil** (RIVM)

- Earlier research linked to this has been [published](#) and studies on risk assessment approaches for mixtures of PFAS in blood are underway.

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Q&A and discussion

After the presentations, participants further discussed:

- The importance of better knowledge on mode of action to avoid regrettable substitution, within the PFAS group but also from PFAS to other groups of chemicals. *“It can give an indication, in an early stage, of what these substances can do.”*
- What (other) type of evidence would be needed in the future to speed up the regulatory process.

Break-out group discussions on policy use of the HBM4EU results

At the end of day 1, the participants were divided into two groups to discuss the relevance of the presented results for policy making. Several important added values were identified as well as additional needs:

- **The data clearly underpin the need for policy action.** For some of the legacy PFAS legislation is already in place (mainly PFOS and PFOA), in the context of REACH and for specific uses (e.g. food items). But this may not be sufficient, as internal exposure levels in humans remain high.
- *“The results are useful to further support a universal PFAS restriction.”*
- *“In some food items, the sum of legacy PFAS levels remains high and based on dietary intake calculations the TWI is easily exceeded. More dietary restrictions may be needed. A safety margin may not be sufficient.”*
- Relevant actions can also be taken in **other policy areas** and are currently under consideration:
- *“There may be an acute need for lowering limits for PFAS in drinking water.”*
- *“Restrictions of PFAS in consumer products are needed to reduce the exposure of the population by eliminating all non-essential uses.”*
- HBM provides **realistic exposure estimations** as input for risk assessments.
- Analysing data from questionnaires and modelling environmental exposures should complement HBM to **identify exposure pathways and local sources**.
- There is also a need to **monitor non-legacy compounds**, with improved analytical methods. Also risk assessments of the non-legacy compounds are needed, including mechanistic data and information on linkage to health outcomes.
- For legacy PFAS it is important to **follow up whether policy measures are effective**, with new HBM data in a representative sample of the EU population. The collected HBM data under HBM4EU will serve as a baseline for future measurements.
- Data from HBM studies in the general population indicate relatively high background concentrations, but there is also a need to better identify and map **hotspot polluted sites**, which are expected to be numerous in Europe.

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3 Day 2 - What opportunities for policy uptake of HBM4EU results?

The second (half) day of the workshop was devoted to policy opportunities for the use of the PFAS results from HBM4EU. The day was introduced by Prof. Dr. **Ilse Loots** (UAntwerp, workshop host).

“Both the project’s results and policy opportunities may be understood broadly. Although the regulatory field is crucial and often the first to think of in a EU context, the output and activities of HBM4EU can be valuable for many different types of policy development.” says Prof. Dr. **Ilse Loots** (UAntwerp).

With a few schemes and illustrations, Ilse Loots highlighted the potential relevance of HBM results in different stages of the policy life cycle, for different policy levels and policy domains, for a diversity of policy instruments, and to trigger actions of non-government actors. “*We also presume that the existence of HBM4EU itself will build confidence in the way the EU and its member states invest in chemicals policy. There is a potential to build trust, also with regard to the PFAS case. An investment in communication and dialogue is very valuable in this respect.*”

In a first part of the second workshop day, two important policy processes with regard to PFAS at the EU-level were presented.

3.1 EU strategy for PFAS

In a first presentation, **Valentina Bertato** (European Commission, DG Environment, Sustainable Chemicals Unit) presented the recently published EU strategy for PFAS. She explained the political inputs that led to the development of the strategy as well as the different actions planned in the context of several EU legislations.

Figure 1: Overview of the different fields in which PFAS actions are/will be taken (Source: Presentation Valentina Bertato, European Commission)

Actions have already started in the context of the Drinking Water Directive, the Groundwater Directive and the Food Contaminants Regulation. With regard to the latter, a discussion has started with the Member States to set maximum levels in food, on the basis of the recent EFSA opinion. Other legislative changes are underway, with the possibility to include limits for PFAS, taking advantage of the on-going review process for the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive, the Sewage Sludge Directive, the Environmental Quality Standards Directive, the Groundwater Directive and the Water Framework Directive.

In her presentation, Valentina Bertato also reflected on the (potential) use of HBM(4EU) results for EU policy making:

*“How can HBM4EU help? It has already helped a lot. All the recent policy initiatives that have been taken were largely driven by a growing concern on human exposure to PFAS, as clearly shown in HBM studies”, says **Valentina Bertato** (European Commission, DG ENV).*

In addition, Valentina Bertato highlighted the importance of having realistic exposure estimations and to better understand exposure pathways, to act where it is most relevant. *“HBM is fundamental to reduce uncertainties and improve the risk assessment on which many of our EU legislations are based.”* Also mixture risk assessment and monitoring of effectiveness of policies and legislations were highlighted as very important uses.

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- [PFAS Staff working document](#) ('PFAS strategy'), as part of [Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability](#)
- [ECHA webpage on PFAS](#)
- [EFSA opinion on PFAS](#)

3.2 Restriction intention for the PFAS group

In a second presentation, **Martijn Beekman** (RIVM, the Netherlands) presented a state of affairs on the intention of several EU countries to restrict PFAS as a group, in the context of REACH. The restriction dossier is being prepared by the Netherlands, Sweden, Germany, Norway and Denmark. The key element or basis for the restriction will be persistency, a property that applies to all PFAS substances. Other concerns that may not apply to all PFAS will further support the restriction, including human toxicity. The goal will be to restrict all **non-essential uses** of PFAS as much as possible.

*“The restriction dossier will mainly describe PFAS uses, tonnages and emissions from PFAS manufacturing and use. In addition, environmental- and HBM data will be used to strengthen the justification for risk reduction measures. These data can probably not be used to directly link to the different sources. But we should demonstrate that there is a need to act.”, says **Martijn Beekman** (RIVM, coordinator of the PFAS group restriction process)*

Martijn Beekman also discussed the formal REACH procedure and expected timing for the dossier on the PFAS group. The restriction intention is now in a preparatory phase (RMOA¹) and will be formally submitted to ECHA's registry of intention in July 2021. From that point, the dossier has to be submitted to ECHA in one-year time.

To ensure that the results of HBM4EU can be fully included, it is best to make them available before November 1, 2021 (!!!).

After submitting the dossier to ECHA, currently foreseen for July 2022, the ECHA committees RAC and SEAC have one-year time to adopt an opinion, including two public consultations. After that, the European Commission prepares a proposal for amending Annex XVII of REACH (3 months), which will be submitted for discussion to the Member States via the REACH Committee. For this last step, no time limit is foreseen. But an adopted decision is to be expected at the earliest in 2025.

In a second part of the presentation, **Kristin Larsson** (KEMI, Sweden) provided more detailed information on the added value of HBM for the PFAS group restriction: *“The new high-quality data from HBM4EU on 12 PFAS in 9 EU countries will be important to describe the current exposure to PFAS in Europe. Data on health effects will also be reviewed for a qualitative human health impact assessment. In addition, we are especially interested in time-trends, HBM data from contaminated sites and from populations in remote areas (to illustrate long range transport). Because targeted analyses of non-regulated PFAS are scarce and often below the detection limits, also non-specific analyses and non-target or suspect screenings will be very important to support the justification for the restriction.”*

Kristin Larsson also identified several future data needs, i.e. the need to i) further characterise the baseline for PFAS exposure in the European population at the time when the restriction enters into force, not only for targeted but also for non-specific analyses; ii) quality control for non-specific

¹ RMOA = [Regulatory Management Option Analysis](#)

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analyses and analysis of total PFAS by inter-laboratory comparisons; and iii) characterisation of unidentified PFAS. Data and evidence on non-regulated PFAS will be very important for this restriction.

- More information on the PFAS group restriction can be found on [ECHA's website](#).

Q&A and discussion

After the presentations on the PFAS Strategy and PFAS group restriction, several questions and discussion topics were raised by the participants.

- How flexible will the concept of essential use be used? And who is developing the concept and criteria?
- *“To review everything and decide on what are essential uses is very thorough and time consuming. But then things may change. Essential uses may become non-essential because of technological advances. Once you establish the rules, how quickly can you respond to readdressing derogations or essential use decisions? What sort of time windows do you anticipate?”*
- Will it be possible to align the various regulations with the TWI set by EFSA?
- *“In the Drinking Water Directive, a limit value of 0,1 ug/L for sum of PFAS was decided, but – depending on the mix of PFAS – this will not be sufficiently protective compared to the EFSA TWI for four PFAS. Will there be some refinement?”*
- *“Limits in products will be covered by the REACH restriction? I assume this will be based on concepts such as ‘as low as technically achievable’, in combination with ‘essential use’? But will there be a link with the TWI from EFSA?”*
- Are discussions ongoing to map PFAS polluted sites, at the initiative of the EU, or is this a responsibility for the member states?
- The effects of the EU regulations will only become visible within several years, and in the longer term an international approach will be needed. At the same time, HBM shows the urgency, i.e. a relatively high exposure in the general population for various PFAS, compared to available health-based guidelines. What additional actions are needed in the short term? Informing citizens? Exposure prevention? Convincing industry and sectors to take action?
- Will the EU fund long-term monitoring of the PFAS, to monitor effectiveness of policy actions? E.g. with HBM, which gives an integrated view on human exposure? And what would be the relevant time in between sampling periods?
- PFAS will, most probably, also be a priority within the PARC project, the successor of HBM4EU. **Can inter-laboratory comparisons for PFAS total and non-specific analysis be organised in the context of PARC?**
- Exposure data is clearly stated as a data need for the EU policy processes, but **would you agree that more information on human toxicokinetics is crucial for PFAS as well and is a future data need?** To support e.g. evidence on bioaccumulation?
- **Wouldn't it be more efficient to use the authorisation route instead of restriction?** That way, industry will have to proof that their products are safe?

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- **Would it be possible to require producers of PFAS to make reference chemicals as well as analytical-chemical methods for human biomonitoring samples available**, e.g. to ECHA or JRC, in order to facilitate the shift from suspect/non-target to targeted monitoring.
- **Will samples be stored in biobanks to measure ‘back in time’ when new, better methods become available?**

3.3 Added value of HBM(4EU) for the national, regional and local level

After a short break, **Karen Van Campenhout** and **Hans Reynders** (Government of Flanders, Belgium) illustrated the relevance of HBM studies and results for national and regional policy making. Since 2001, Flanders has a large scale HBM-program, i.e. the Flemish Environment and Health Study (FLEHS). Over the past 20 years several FLEHS cycles have been conducted, both in the general population and in hotspot areas and the results are an important basis for the Flemish environmental health policy.

PFAS are monitored in Flanders in the general population since FLEHS II (2007-2011) and caused growing concern in more recent years. Mainly because of the lowering of the health-based guidance values, but also due to other arguments, such as exposure-effect associations found in the data and associations with the consumption of home-grown food. These and other findings have led to the development of a regional- as well as a national action plan in 2020. The action plan includes a coordinated approach between the different policy actors, knowledge exchange, source control (evaluation of permits and better enforcement), environmental monitoring, development of a soil policy for PFAS, additional and targeted research into human exposure and health effects, and communication and awareness raising.

*“It is not always easy to convince policy makers to keep on investing in HBM. But the PFAS case is another good example of the added value of having a regional HBM program. Also European cooperation, such as in the context of HBM4EU and PARC, are very important in this respect”, says **Hans Reynders** (Government of Flanders, Belgium)*

As a second illustration, **Anna Maria Ingelido** (Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Italy) reflected on the previous presentation from her experience from a local case in the Veneto region, in the North of Italy. In this region, PFAS contamination of the drinking water became known in 2013, potentially affecting 125.000 inhabitants. The contamination resulted primarily from industrial emissions from a chemical plant in the area that produced the substances. It had affected ground water, surface water and drinking water. The Veneto region set up an intersectoral working group, to identify the most appropriate mitigation and remediation measures and to investigate the extent to which the contamination could adversely affect the health of the affected population.

*“HBM supported the work of the local authorities in confirming exposure, helping to better identify the most affected areas and to identify the main risk factors in order to be able to give indications to citizens to limit their personal exposure. It also provided a basis for a health surveillance plan, to evaluate effectiveness of the interventions. Two years later, concentrations declined significantly in the region.”, says **Anna Maria Ingelido** (Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Italy).*

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Q&A and discussion

In the discussion, other similar cases were mentioned by the participants, e.g. in Austria and the US. And a few important issues were raised:

- When confronted with a (new) contamination, be it at the national, local or EU level, **transparent and pro-active communication is very important**. People want to know whether they are exposed, where it comes from, whether they didn't know before, and what they can do to prevent exposure. HBM studies can be very important in answering some of these questions. But it can also be a vehicle to start a conversation on complex issues such as PFAS exposure. In the FLEHS study in Flanders, **communication rules** were decided up front, before results came available. The rules were jointly developed by the researchers and commissioning government, and are updated at the start of each cycle. It provides a basis for effective and supported communication. Also within HBM4EU a [strategy for communicating new results from aligned studies](#) was developed, partly based on the FLEHS experience.
- It is expected that more **PFAS hotspots** will come to the attention in the coming years:
- *"We have a background contamination in Europe, which is already at a level for which we have considerable concerns. And then we have, I think in all EU countries and globally, contamination issues. The number of cases is clearly increasing, e.g. industrial cases, but also firefighting training sites, airports, etc. We know already a bit, but not everything. And not all countries have already looked into this problem."*
- HBM4EU could play a role in sharing experiences among EU countries and start a (proactive) mapping of potential hotspots. That way it could support the EC's PFAS strategy, in which it is a proposed action but for which the EC is largely dependent on the member states.

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3.4 Workshop's contributions to HBM4EU's ambitions

At the end of the second workshop day, **Dr. Marike Kolossa-Gehring** (UBA, HBM4EU coordinator) expressed her gratitude to all contributors and participants and formulated some conclusions.

“The workshop created a very nice interface between HBM4EU work and regulatory activities. It raised for all persons involved, the awareness of HBM4EU results, but also on the time scale for effective use of our results. We also received information on the policy cycle and this opened our eyes for the different aspects and policy instruments which we should work on and use. It also underlined the need for continued HBM at EU level. And gave us inspiration for additional research questions and needs for PARC. Also, at the national level, there is clearly a need for action, e.g. in communication, in elucidating most pressing issues. But in the end, we will need action at the EU- and international level. We obviously have here an urgent health issue that has to be addressed as urgently as possible.” **Marike Kolossa-Gehring** (UBA, HBM4EU coordinator).

Additional information shared in the chat

- Canada has recently announced that they will regulate PFAS as a class. More specifically the authorities announced they will: (1) continue to invest in PFAS-related research and monitoring, (2) collect and examine information on implementing a class-based approach, and (3) review developments in other jurisdictions. The goal is to publish a “State of PFAS” report summarising all available information on the class of PFAS within the next two years. Of potential interest for HBM4EU: Stakeholders interested in providing feedback on the proposed plan, especially regarding “challenges or opportunities” are welcome to contact the agencies to send their comments.
- New PFAS-Tox Database has been launched by a group of universities and NGOs. “Publicly available resource provides systematic evidence map covering 742 toxicity studies on 29 per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS); features dozens of studies on ‘purportedly safer’ PFAS; findings show adverse health impacts studied for wide range of PFAS; experts call for class-based management of all PFAS.” Of relevance for HBM4EU: To ensure uptake of HBM4EU PFAS toxicity studies in the database.
- Our partners from ISCIII, in HBM4EU, are doing inter-laboratory comparisons for PFAS and other HBM4EU priority substance groups. More information can be found in HBM4EU's Online Library. The EEA is currently working with ISCIII to publish on the website the European HBM laboratory network as an interactive map.
- HBM4EU is also doing interesting work for citizens: factsheets on 3 different chemicals were produced (Cr VI, phthalates and bisphenols) together with one-page infographics. We are currently working to finalise 8 more factsheets (including PFAS) which should be out soon. We have also produced video animations and videos on chemicals. A video on PFAS will be out in Summer. And focus groups were organised in Austria, Portugal, Ireland, UK, the Netherlands, Cyprus, Denmark and Hungary.

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- Also Research briefs for a technical audience are being produced. More Research briefs will become available in 2021 and 2022.
- An overview of HBM4EU inputs to public consultations is available on the website.
- People interested in receiving more news can register for receiving the new Science Digest Newsletter and HBM4EU newsletter.

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4 Conclusions

On 28-29 April 2021 an online workshop was organised for HBM4EU experts and risk assessors and managers from the European Commission, EU-agencies and national authorities, to discuss first, preliminary results from HBM4EU on PFAS as well as policy opportunities, in a confidential setting.

Participants were offered up to date information on HBM4EU results and activities, including information on the HBM studies from various countries in Europe that have been aligned to generate EU-wide HBM data ('aligned studies'), the HBM4EU online dashboard, studies on health impact of PFAS exposure and mode of action, and PFAS mixture risk assessment.

On the second day of the workshop, several policy actors were invited to present up to date information on recent policy developments and how the results of HBM4EU could contribute to these efforts. Presentations provided information on the European commission's PFAS strategy, the restriction intention for the PFAS group as a whole and policy initiatives at the national level, with examples from two EU member states. These presentations illustrated the relevance and use of HBM at different policy levels and for multiple uses.

Results from HBM4EU clearly support the need for (additional) policy action and the workshop clearly demonstrated the importance of an open and in-depth science-to-policy dialogue between HBM4EU experts, risk managers and risk assessors, across various policy domains and policy levels. Several opportunities for the use of HBM4EU's results were identified, as well as remaining questions and future data needs.

Concrete opportunities for the use of HBM4EU results:

- The most recent and quality controlled HBM data from HBM4EU will be important supportive evidence for the **PFAS group restriction**, to demonstrate that there is a need to act. Also, other results from HBM4EU, e.g. on health effect, mode of action, mixture risk assessment, are highly welcomed to support a qualitative human health risk assessment. Results are preferable submitted by November 1, 2021.
- As a consequence of EFSA's scientific opinion on four PFAS (2020), a **discussion has been started with the EU Member States to set maximum levels in food**. HBM based analyses on the relative importance of exposure routes and sources (via statistical analysis or modelling) could inform this discussion. HBM results were also previously sent to EFSA in the context of a public consultation for the scientific opinion in 2020.
- **Several legislative changes are on the agenda** for the coming years with the potential to include limits for PFAS, i.e. the *Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWT), *Sewage Sludge Directive (SSD), *Environmental Quality Standards Directive (EQSD), *Groundwater Directive (GD) and *Water Framework Directive (WFD). Actions have already been taken in the context of the *Drinking Water Directive, *Groundwater Directive and *Food Contaminants Regulation.
- At the **national level**, HBM4EU results could help to **raise awareness** among the public as well as policy makers that policy action is needed. **Many important competences to reduce exposure are still situated at the national and local level**, including soil and water policy, preventive health, monitoring and enforcement of EU legislation. Actions have been taken in some countries in the last few years, but given the persistency of PFAS sustained attention will be needed for many years.

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- Given the fact that many new policy actions on PFAS are on the table, HBM4EU results can become an important **baseline to follow up effectiveness of policy measures. HBM based indicators** are being developed within HBM4EU to track progress and can be included in state-of-the-environment reporting at EU- and national level. Continued investment in monitoring, ideally with a time interval of 2 to 3 years between data points, would be needed for this purpose.

Open questions and (future) data needs:

- With regard to available HBM data, participants indicated a need to better understand **exposure pathways and (local) sources**, to act where it is most relevant. More detailed statistical analysis is still ongoing within HBM4EU and also exposure modelling would be important to be able to better explain HBM data. For the PFAS group restriction, preparatory work is also ongoing to make an overview of PFAS uses and emissions.
- There is also an urgent need to monitor and study **emerging PFAS, PFAS mixtures and total organic fluorine**. Methods are being developed to monitor exposure, but quality control/inter-laboratory comparison would be needed and can potentially be taken up within the PARC project (HBM4EU's successor). In several EU-countries, biobanks can provide samples to measure 'back in time' when new methods are available. Also, with regard to the study of health impact of PFAS exposure, new approaches are needed to advance our knowledge more quickly and efficiently.
- At the **local level**, several **contamination cases** have come to light in recent years and it is expected that many more will be added in the coming years. From the EU-level, establishing an inventory and a screening of potential cases as well as exchanging good practices would be useful.

In conclusion, there seems to be a **political urgency** on PFAS, after many years of research. Since 2019, there has been a fairly rapid policy development at EU-level, in which the focus is mainly shifting from the regulated PFAS (mainly PFOS and PFOA) to other, emerging PFAS, often used as substitutes. Despite the uncertainties and knowledge gaps that still exist with regard to these emerging substances, far-reaching restrictions and limit values are being considered. **HBM studies have contributed to putting PFAS high on the political agenda and HBM4EU results can further support ongoing EU processes.**

Also, in **various EU Member States**, the PFAS problem receives a lot of attention and actions are being taken. However, at the national level, the focus remains mainly on the legacy PFAS (such as PFOS and PFOA). These substances will remain for a long time in the environment and human exposure is only slowly decreasing. In most cases, an integrated and coordinated approach will be needed involving both environmental and public health policy departments. Also, in this context, **local and national HBM studies are very useful to inform policy makers and citizens, and can be a vehicle for (pro)active communication on environmental health risks.**

Finally, in this workshop some advice was formulated on the communication of 'aligned studies' results. Active communication of the results, as well as communication on the existence of HBM4EU itself, can build confidence in the way the EU and its member states invest in chemicals policy.

5 Participants

In total, 56 participants took part in the workshop, with a very stable number of participants during both half days. A participant list is included in Annex 1.

All participants were invited in person, with the aim of having a limited number but broad diversity of relevant perspectives. Including **HBM4EU partners** (organisers and presenters), **Principal Investigators (PI's) of the national studies** contributing to the PFAS aligned studies, representatives from **EU agencies and the European Commission**, and representatives from organisations working on the **PFAS group restriction intention**. See figure 2.

Figure 2: overview of the types of participants to the workshop

Participants were asked to speak in their own name, inspired by their own professional expertise. By underlining the freedom to speak, we wanted to reassure participants that they were not expected to speak with a mandate of their organisation. In addition, participants were explicitly asked not to disclose confidential information shared during the workshop. Presentations (excluding confidential information) were made available after the workshop.

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6 Why a closed and confidential workshop?

Part of the results presented were not yet publicly available at the time of the workshop. Confidentiality was a condition for discussing these results. This also provided the opportunity to ask advice from a limited group of stakeholders on the formulation of key messages for public and targeted communication, which will be organised in a later stage.

In addition, we wanted to provide a safe environment for the free exchange of ideas between HBM experts, risk assessors and risk managers, across the various policy domains, on how the results can be used most effectively within planned and ongoing policy processes.

7 Workshop evaluation

After the workshop, an online and anonymous evaluation form was sent to all participants. We received 32 individual responses, out of 56 participants.

All respondents indicated to be 'very satisfied' or 'satisfied' with the **workshop's goal and focus**. The **quality of the presentations** of both part 1 and part 2 of the workshop was considered 'very satisfactory' or 'satisfactory'.

Also, the **room for discussion and input** was much appreciated by the respondents. To the question 'will you use in your organisation/network what you have learned during the workshop?' 23 answered 'absolutely!' and 9 'yes, I think so'.

In the free remark zone of the survey, a respondent indicated that more opportunities should be created to have science-policy dialogues on priority substances: "*good format to learn quickly on a broad range of themes related to PFAS. I look forward to similar workshops on other priority compounds*". Another respondent added: "*interactions between (bio/chemo)scientists, social scientists and policy makers is of great added value*".

The workshop on PFAS was considered timely: "*I think the timing of the workshop fits very well within the sequence of events regarding PFAS policy*". A follow-up workshop on PFAS was suggested: "*Once the statistical analysis on determinants of exposure are completed, additional discussions could be helpful in identifying policy opportunities to reduce exposure to these PFAS*".

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8 Annex 1: Participant list

	Name	Institution
1	Greet Schoeters	VITO, BE
2	Marike Kolossa-Gehring	UBA, DE
3	Robert Barouki (Wednesday)	Inserm, FR
4	Argelia Castaño Calvo	ISCIII, National Center for E&H, ES
5	Eva Govarts	VITO, BE
6	Jos Bessems	VITO, BE
7	Ann Colles	VITO, BE
8	Liese Gilles	VITO, BE
9	Joana Lobo Vicente	European Environment Agency (EEA)
10	Ilse Loots	University of Antwerp, BE
11	Ann Crabbé	University of Antwerp, BE
12	Dries Coertjens	University of Antwerp, BE
13	Maria Uhl	Environment Agency Austria (EAA), AT
14	Wieneke Bil	RIVM, NL
15	Stella Fragki	RIVM, NL
16	Marco Zeilmaker	RIVM, NL
17	ThorÞórhallur Ingi Halldórsson	University of Iceland, IC
18	Tony Fletcher	Public Health England, UK
19	Karen Van Campenhout	Dep. of Environment, Flanders, BE
20	Hans Reynders	Dep. of Environment, Flanders, BE
21	Veerle Vanheusden	DG SANTE, European Commission
22	Frans Verstraete	DG SANTE, European Commission
23	Valentina Bertato	DG ENV, European Commission
24	Bert Leemans	DG ENV, European Commission
25	Enrique Garcia John	DG ENV, European Commission
26	Kobe Andrej	DG ENV, European Commission
27	Sofie Norager	DG RTD, European Commission
28	Mariann Karcza	DG RTD, European Commission
29	Xenia Trier	European Environment Agency (EEA)
30	Roser Gasol	European Environment Agency (EEA)
31	Marco Binaglia	European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

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	Name	Institution
32	Jane Caley (Wednesday)	European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)
33	Charmaine Ajao (Wednesday)	European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)
34	Anna Mazzolini (Thursday)	European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)
35	Line Småstuen Haug	Norwegian Institute of Public Health
36	Cathrine Thomsen	Norwegian Institute of Public Health
37	Katerina Gabriel	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, GR
38	Spyros Karakitsios	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, GR
39	Antonis Stratidakis	University School for Advanced Studies Pavia, Italy
40	Maria Perikli	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, GR
41	Elly Den Hond	PIH
42	Carmen Franken	PIH
43	Nina Vogel (only Wednesday)	UBA
44	Antje Gerofke	UBA, DE
45	Susana Pedraza-Diaz	ISCIII, National Center for E&H, ES
46	Ana Cañas (Wednesday)	ISCIII, National Center for E&H, ES
47	Sanna Lignell	Swedish Food Agency
48	Lubica Murinova	Slovak Medical University (SZU)
49	Lucia Fabelova	Slovak Medical University (SZU)
50	Martijn Beekman (Thursday)	RIVM, NL
51	Maryam Zare Jeddi	RIVM, NL
52	Kristin Larsson	KEMI, SE
53	Angelika Baumbusch	Norwegian Environment Agency
54	Cecile Blom (Thursday)	Norwegian Environment Agency
55	Anna Maria Ingelido	ISS, Italy
56	Annalisa Abballe	ISS, Italy

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9 Annex 2: Workshop program

How can human biomonitoring help to protect
our health from PFAS exposure?

Science-policy workshop on policy uptake of HBM4EU results

Wednesday 28 April 2021 (13:30-16:45) and Thursday 29 April 2021 (9:30-12:30)

Within HBM4EU, knowledge and expertise in the field of human biomonitoring is brought together and further expanded. The PFAS substances group is one of the [HBM4EU Priority Substance Groups](#) and has received increasing attention from policymakers in recent years.

In a **noon-to-noon online workshop**, HBM4EU aims to actively stimulate the dialogue and transmission of information between scientists, risk assessors and risk managers on the outputs of the HBM4EU project, specifically related to PFAS.

During the **first half-day workshop**, participants are offered up to date information on HBM4EU results, including information on the HBM studies from various countries in Europe that have been aligned to generate EU-wide HBM data.

PART 1 (Wednesday 28 April 2021, 13:30-16:35)		
Messages from HBM4EU on PFAS		
13:30 - 13:45	Introduction to the workshop's programme and its ambitions Welcome and short introduction to HBM4EU	Ilse Loots, UAntwerp, workshop chair Marieke Kolossa-Gehring, UBA, HBM4EU coordinator
13:45 - 14:00	Overview of activities on PFAS in HBM4EU	Maria Uhl, EAA, chemical group leader PFAS
14:00 - 14:20	EU wide internal exposure levels of PFAS: results from existing HBM data + output from aligned studies	Eva Govarts, VITO
14:20 - 14:40	Discussion on main messages for communication of the aligned studies' results on PFAS	Moderator: Greet Schoeters, VITO (pillar I lead)
14:40 - 14:55	<i>Break</i>	
14:55 - 15:25	What does HBM4EU contribute to our knowledge on the health impact of current PFAS exposure? Serum cholesterol and its association with PFOS/PFOA exposure: the riddle for risk assessors Epidemiological findings on PFAS in HBM4EU	Stella Fragki, RIVM ThorÞórhallur Ingi Halldórsson, University of Iceland
15:25 - 15:40	Risk assessment approaches of PFAS mixtures	Wieneke Bil (RIVM)
15:40 - 15:55	Q&A	Robert Barouki, INSERM (pillar III lead)
15:55 - 16:30	Discussion in break-out groups, reflecting on the policy use of HBM4EU results	

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PART 1 (Wednesday 28 April 2021, 13:30-16:35)		
Messages from HBM4EU on PFAS		
16:30 - 16:40	Short plenary feedback on the discussion in the break-out groups by the reporters	Greet Schoeters, VITO Robert Barouki, INSERM
16:40 - 16:45	Outlook on tomorrow's programme	Ilse Loots, UAntwerpen

During the **second half-day** of the workshop, several policy actors are invited to present up to date information on recent policy developments and how HBM4EU (or its successor PARC) could contribute to these efforts. This second part of the workshop includes presentations on the European commission's PFAS strategy, the restriction intention for the PFAS substance group and an exemplary presentation of a member state undertaking complementary policy initiatives on PFAS, inspired by HBM.

PART 2 (Thursday 29 April, 9:30-12:30)		
What opportunities for policy uptake can HBM4EU bring?		
9:30 - 9:40	Introduction to today's programme	Ilse Loots, UAntwerp, workshop chair
9:40 - 10:00	PFAS strategy of the European commission	Valentina Bertato, DG ENV
10:00 - 10:10	Q&A	Ilse Loots, UAntwerpen
10:10 - 10:35	Presentations on the PFAS group restriction proposal <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PFAS group restriction intention and information needs • Added value of HBM for the PFAS group restriction 	Martijn Beekman, RIVM Kristin Larsson, KEMI
10:35 - 11:10	Q&A and discussion on the use of HBM(4EU results) in current policy processes	Ilse Loots, UAntwerpen
11:10 - 11:25	<i>Break</i>	
11:25 - 11:40	Illustrating the HBM results' relevance for national/regional initiatives: the PFAS case in Flanders (Belgium).	Hans Reynders and Karen Van Campenhout, DOMG (Flanders/Belgium)
11:40 - 11:50	Opening up the discussion with first reactions from Italy: the Veneto case	Anna Maria Ingelido, Istituto Superiore di Sanità (Italy)
11:50 - 12:15	Plenary discussion	Ilse Loots, UAntwerpen
12:15 - 12:25	Workshop contributions to HBM4EU's ambitions	Marika Kolossa-Gehring, UBA
12:25 - 12:30	Closure	Ilse Loots, UAntwerpen Greet Schoeters, VITO